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4 **Title**

5 Immune response accelerated telomere shortening during early life stage of a passerine bird, the
6 blue tit (*Cyanistes caeruleus*)

7

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23

24 **Abstract**

25 Dealing with infections is a daily challenge for wild animals. Empirical data show increasing of ROS
26 production during immune response. This could have consequences on telomeres length, end parts
27 of linear chromosomes, commonly used as proxy for good health and aging. Telomere length
28 dynamics may reflect the cost associated to physiological responses. In this study, immune system
29 of blue tit (*Cyanistes caeruleus*) nestlings were experimentally challenged through a
30 Polyinosinic:polycytidylic acid (Poly I:C) injection, a synthetic double-stranded RNA that mimics a
31 virus, activating the pathway of immune response triggered via the toll-like receptors 3 (TLR3).
32 This path is known to form ROS downstream. Immune response was quantified by white cell counts

33 in blood, while brain lipoperoxidation has been evaluated as indicator of oxidative damage. Finally,
34 individuals' telomere length shortening between day 8 and 15 after hatching was measured in
35 erythrocytes. Challenged nestlings showed increased leukocytes number when compared to control
36 (treated with a saline solution), lower brain lipid peroxidation (likely as a result of a compensatory
37 mechanism after oxidative stress burst) and accelerated telomere shortening. These findings
38 support the "ageing cost of infections pathway" hypothesis, which supposes a role of infections in
39 quick biological ageing.

40

41 **Introduction**

42 Telomeres are parts of genomic DNA at the end of linear chromosomes, made of repeated
43 sequence (TTAGGG)_n in vertebrates [1]. They play an important role in chromosome stability,
44 protecting them from being detected as DNA double-strand breaks, stopping degradation and
45 fusion with other chromosome ends [2]. Telomeres length decreases progressively according to cell
46 divisions, due to incomplete replication of the DNA end during lagging strand DNA synthesis by
47 polymerases (enzymes that catalyze the synthesis of DNA), a mechanism called "end replication
48 problem" [3]. Another mechanism by which telomeres may shorten is via oxidative stress [4],
49 where the level of reactive oxygen species –ROS– are higher than the capacity of antioxidant
50 defense, thus leading to excessive ROS exposure [5]. Reactive oxygen species can be generated
51 from exogenous sources as pollutants [6], or endogenous factors like mitochondria metabolism [7].
52 Telomeres are especially sensitive to oxidative damage [8], because ROS specifically target their
53 guanine bases forming DNA lesions [9]. These bases modifications can initiate DNA base excision
54 repair pathways (BER) by DNA glycosylase, an enzyme which catalyzes the removal of damaged
55 nucleotides [10] and thereby parts of telomere. Although telomere shortening seems to be a
56 general rule, also telomere lengthening has been observed [11], for example in red blood cells of
57 house sparrows (*Passer domesticus*)[12], Magellanic penguins (*Spheniscus magellanicus*) [13],
58 Seychelles warblers (*Acrocephalus sechellensis*)[14], humans (*Homo sapiens*) [15], and in buccal
59 mucosa cells of edible dormice (*Glis glis*)[16]. Lengthening may occur because the activity of
60 telomerase enzyme (which maintains telomere length by adding new sequences)[17], high
61 turnover in hematopoietic cells[18], or other reasons yet to be clarified. Observations of both
62 telomere shortening and lengthening during ageing suggest we should rethink telomere length as a
63 length dynamic which reflect current individual's state and its physiological trade-offs, rather than
64 a progressive and unstoppable shortening according growth. For instance, malaria infection by
65 *Plasmodium falciparum* increased telomere shortening in blood cells during the first three months
66 after infection in humans [15]. However, following infection, CDKN2A expression (a gene linked to
67 cell senescence) declined, resulting in increasing telomerase activity that gradually restored over
68 one year the telomere length as pre-infection levels. Therefore, although telomere length has
69 become a biomarker to estimate health status [19], telomere length dynamics may better
70 underline processes related to interactions between individuals and their physiological challenges,
71 as well as their future life-history strategies and adaptive responses [20].

72 The effect of environmental stressors on telomeres length could be particularly important during
73 early life stages, when telomere loss is already strongly pronounced [21] and when animal are

74 more vulnerable. Early life exposure to pathogens can be a challenge, particularly in natural bird
75 populations and in nestlings without protection of feathers, which are susceptible to infection e.g.
76 from vectors such as mosquitoes [21] or ticks [22]. Parasites and infections may trigger immune
77 system increasing telomere shortening through direct cost of immune activation and reduced
78 investment in tissue maintenance [22]. Furthermore, an increase in ROS is a feature of many viral
79 infections, and can be caused by direct effects of virus on cells and indirect effects of inflammatory
80 responses [23]. Therefore, infections may represent an important stressor that could increase
81 telomere shortening.

82 In this study, the effect of immune response on telomere length dynamic has been addressed: blue
83 tit (*Cyanistes caeruleus*) nestlings were experimentally challenged using polyinosinic:polycytidylic
84 acid (Poly I:C) as model compound to mimic a viral infection. Poly I:C is a double stranded RNA
85 similar as some viruses, which is recognized by the toll-like receptors 3 (TLR3) of macrophages,
86 lymphocytes and dendritic cells, inducing interferon α and β as responses [24] and generation of
87 ROS for phosphorylation and nuclear translocation of STAT1 and STAT2 [25], key components of
88 the transcription factor complex in interferons signaling pathways [26]. The Toll-like receptor 3,
89 involved in detection of pathogens [27], is also present in many other cells, such as epithelial cells
90 [28] and erythrocyte [29]. We hypothesize activation of immune system through a simulated
91 infection lead to generation of ROS and accelerates telomere shortening in exposed birds.

92

93 **Methods**

94 **(a) Routine in field**

95 The study was conducted over the spring of 2022. Wild pairs of blue tit (*Cyanistes caeruleus*) freely
96 breed in artificial nest boxes in Wageningen (51.981063, 5.636866) and Rhenen (51.973095,
97 5.577511), in Netherlands. The field sites count 100 nest boxes installed in 2021 along roads,
98 about 3 m in height, in oak trees (*Quercus robur*). From middle of March, boxes were routinely
99 checked to monitor the stage of breeding. In total, 32 nestlings from 8 different nests were
100 included in experiment. At day 8 post hatching (hatching day as "day 1"), chicks nails were colored
101 with nail polish to recognize individuals during development. Morphometric measures (mass, tarsus
102 and wing length) were collected at day 8, and subsequently 40 μ l of blood was sampled from
103 brachial vein using 25 G needles (Sterican®) and 75 μ l sodium-heparinized capillary tubes
104 (VITREX®). Blood samples were centrifuged (microcentrifuge VWR® MiniStar silverline) for 10
105 minutes at 2000 g to separate plasma from red blood cells, and samples were stored at -80 °C. On
106 the day 13 after hatch, two random chicks from each nest were challenged with an intra-muscular
107 injection of 10 μ l of Poly I:C (Sigma Aldrich), and two others received a saline solution as control,
108 using sterile syringes with 27 G needles (Sterican®). Therefore, 4 animals in each nest were used
109 for this study. Poly I:C salt was diluted in saline water and injected in pectoral muscle with a dose
110 of 2 μ g/kg body weight. This value has been chosen according previous studies on house sparrows
111 (*Passer domesticus*) [30] and barnacle goslings (*Branta leucopsis*) [31], which have demonstrated
112 this dose is not lethal but capable to trigger immune response. Poly I:C solution was prepared fresh
113 every day by resuspending the salt in sterile saline at a concentration of 2 mg/ml, until complete

154 characteristics [38]. The % of leukocytes populations relative to erythrocytes was calculated for
155 each animal as $\{[(n^\circ \text{ leukocytes}) - (n^\circ \text{ erythrocytes})] / ((n^\circ \text{ erythrocytes}))\} * 100$.

156

157 **(d) Oxidative stress assay**

158 Whole brain lipoperoxidation was used as oxidative stress biomarker [39]. The Lipotiss test
159 (Diacron International, Grosseto, Italy) was used to assess lipoperoxidation. The method is based
160 on peroxides ability to promote oxidation of Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} . The produced ion binds to thiocyanate,
161 developing a pink color complex photometrically measurable. Procedures followed manufacturer's
162 instructions with minor adjustment according Terraneo and coauthors [40]: 200 mg of pre-mixed
163 tissue were homogenized in 0.5 ml of Milli-Q water, centrifuged 5 min at 15000g and washed three
164 times with Milli-Q water. After removing the supernatant, 500 μl of R1 reagent (mixture of
165 indicators) was added and vials were mixed and centrifuged 5 min at 1400g. Afterwards, 250 μl of
166 supernatant was added in a 96-well plate (Cellstar®, 655-180) together with a standard curve
167 (plus a blank) made of 4 concentrations of 4000 $\mu\text{Eq/L}$ tertbutylhydroperoxide diluted 250 μl of
168 reagent R1. To the solutions have been added 10 μl of reagent R2 (ferrous ions solution) diluted in
169 a ratio 1:4 with reagent R1. After 5 min of incubation at 37 °C, optical density was read at $\lambda=505$
170 nm using a spectrophotometer (Tecan, Infinite-M nano⁺). Concentration of lipoperoxides was
171 calculated and expressed as nanoequivalent of hydroperoxydes (ROOH) per grams of tissue. All
172 individuals in study were analyzed on the same single plate.

173

174 **(e) Statistical Analysis**

175 Statistical analyzes were conducted in R (version 4.3.1). To compare immune response between
176 control and treatment group, a linear mixed effects model was fitted using the ratio leukocytes-
177 erythrocytes as response variable [41], and type of treatment (Poly I:C or saline) plus body
178 condition at day 15 as independent variables. Individual's body condition was calculated by dividing
179 body mass by tarsus length raised to cube [42]; it is a common measure of energy reserves and
180 health status in birds, representing animal mass corrected for its structural size [43]. To
181 investigate if immune response led to a change in oxidative state, brain lipid peroxidation level was
182 used as dependent variable in a new model, while the ratio between number of leukocytes and
183 erythrocyte, and body condition as independent variables. Finally, to examine whether Poly I:C
184 challenge affected telomere shortening between day 8 and 15, a new linear mixed model was used,
185 with telomere shortening rate as dependent variable. Treatment, growth in mass between day 8
186 and 15 (calculated as: $\{[(\text{Mass}_{15} - \text{Mass}_8) / (\text{Mass}_8)] * 100\}$) and body condition at day 15 have
187 been set as independent variables. Growth was included because according to theoretical models,
188 as cell divisions increase telomere length decreases [44]. In all models nest of origin was used as
189 random effect. The 'lmer' function in 'lme4' package [45] was used to build the models, while, to
190 test the significance of the main predictor variables, we used the 'lmerTest' package [46].
191 Significance was taken at $\alpha = 0.05$. Hypothesis of homoscedasticity has been tested and confirmed
192 with a F-test of equality of variances and assumption of normal distribution of model's residual with
193 a Shapiro-Wilk normality test.

194

195 **Results**

196 The results of the first model revealed Poly I:C treatment significantly increased leukocytes number
197 compared to control (Table and Figure 1). This finding supports the hypothesis of immune response
198 after treatment. Body condition at day 15 had no significant effect on the ratio leukocytes-
199 erythrocytes, indicating immune response was primarily driven by treatment rather than the
200 animal physical condition.

Table 1. Model estimates for effect of treatment on leukocytes/erythrocytes ratio

Predictors	Estimates	CI	p
Intercept	-2.13	-8.28 – 4.02	0.465
Treatment (Poly I:C)	0.68	0.09 – 1.28	0.028
Body condition at day 15	0.85	-1.98 – 3.68	0.526

P-values < 0.05 are indicated in bold. Predictors are scaled.

201

Figure 1. Control and treatment immune responses.

202

203 *Figure 1. Boxplots of scaled number of leukocytes compare to erythrocytes at day 15 for control a*
204 *treatment.*

205 The following model evaluated brain lipoperoxidation as function of immune response. The output
206 (Table 2) showed a marginally negative relationship between leukocytes number and
207 lipoperoxidation. Through a stepwise approach that removed body condition as independent
208 variable (not statistically significant), the outcome of the simplified model highlighted a negative
209 covariation between number of leukocytes in blood and brain lipoperoxidation. This trend suggests
210 how in our dataset higher immune response is associated with lower oxidative damage (Figure 2).

Table 2. Model estimates of effect of leukocytes/erythrocytes ratio on lipoperoxidation

Predictors	Estimates	CI	p
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Intercept	1.01	-0.20 – 2.22	0.095
White cells proportion	-0.97	-1.99 – 0.05	0.062
Body condition at day 15	0.01	-0.37 – 0.39	0.953

Simplified model without accounting body conditions

Predictors	Estimates	CI	<i>p</i>
Intercept	0.08	-0.48 – 0.31	0.653
White cells proportion	-0.40	-0.80 – -0.01	0.046

P-values < 0.05 are indicated in bold. Predictors are scaled.

Figure 2. Regression between brain lipoperoxidation and leukocytes number.

211

212 *Figure 2. Overall regression between brain lipoperoxidation at day 15 and immune response*
 213 *estimated as number of leucocytes compare to erythrocytes in blood smears at day 15.*

214

215 The third model evaluated the effect of treatment on telomere length dynamic between day 8 and
 216 day 15. Challenged animals experienced a more pronounced reduction in telomere length
 217 compared to control (Table and Figure 3). Body condition at day 15 and growth mass did not
 218 influenced telomere lengths.

Table 3. Model estimates of effect of treatment on blue tit telomere length dynamic

Predictors	Estimates	CI	<i>p</i>
Intercept	0.41	-0.09 – 0.91	0.102
Treatment (Poly I:C)	-0.79	-1.53 – -0.06	0.036
Growth	0.04	-0.35 – 0.43	0.837
Body condition at day 15	-0.21	-0.60 – 0.19	0.286

P-values < 0.05 are indicated in bold. Predictors are scaled.

219

Figure 3. Control and treatment telomere length variation.

220
221 *Figure 3. Boxplots of scaled telomere length variations in % between day 8 and 15. Values greater*
222 *than 0 correspond to telomere lengthening, negative values to shortening.*

223

224 **Discussion**

225 This study revealed how activation of immune system through viral-like compound Poly I:C could
226 have had an impact on telomere length of blue tit nestlings. In fact, telomere shortening in
227 challenged chicks was significantly accelerated when compared to siblings in control.

228 First, we validated if treatment triggered immune system as expected, since Poly I:C induce an
229 innate immune response [47] promoting activation of peripheral blood leukocytes [48]. This has
230 been proved comparing number of leukocytes between treatment and control animals after
231 challenge. In our study, treatment increased leukocytes numbers, indicating immune response.

232 Secondly, we investigated whether immune response increased oxidative stress. This have been
233 previously reported [49], as well as apoptotic cell death through formation of ROS after Poly I:C
234 exposure [50]. Indeed, Poly I:C RNA binds the TLR3 receptor involved in antiviral and
235 inflammatory responses, leading to ROS generation needed for activation of macrophages' immune
236 responses [25]. In the current study, brain lipoperoxidation was used as oxidative stress
237 biomarker. Free radicals in fact, bind membrane lipids causing peroxidation and generation of
238 highly reactive and electrophilic unsaturated aldehydes, as Malondialdehyde (MDA) and 4-
239 Hydroxynonenal (HNE) [51]. Brain, with its high oxygen consumption and lipid-rich content, is very
240 susceptible to oxidative stress damage [52]. In fact, it has the second highest lipid content after
241 adipose tissue [53]. Previous studies have shown how Poly I:C in rats increased brain lipid
242 peroxidation [54]. Opposite to what we expected, we found a negative relationship between
243 immune response and lipoperoxidation: this was lower when the number of leucocytes in blood was
244 higher. Nevertheless, in a study published by He and coauthors, fish (*Scophthalmus maximus*) fed
245 with Poly I:C had lower liver MDA content than control [55], which would suggested treatment
246 triggered also anti-oxidative-stress activity. We hypothesize therefore that Poly I:C could have

247 initiated an immune response with consequent increased oxidative stress. Subsequently, by the
248 time we measured lipoperoxidation levels in brain, compensatory mechanisms might already had
249 been activated to mitigate further damages. In brain, astrocytes providing antioxidant support to
250 neurons through the Nrf2 pathway and regulation of a cohort of antioxidants genes; furthermore,
251 many neuronal antioxidant genes enabling that increases in ROS are knocked down by enhanced
252 antioxidant capacity of both glutathione and thioredoxin-peroxiredoxin systems [56]. These
253 homeostatic mechanisms therefore may have activated after the oxidative stress burst because
254 treatment, enhancing antioxidant or repair processes and reducing lipoperoxidation two days after
255 exposure. Finally, we established a Poly I:C effect on telomere length dynamics: treatment group
256 showed higher telomere shortening compared to control. Previous evidences suggests viral
257 infections are associated with telomere attrition, however, the degree to which any associations are
258 causal remains unclear [57]. Interestingly, a previous study found no association between
259 herpesvirus infection and telomere shortening in magnificent frigatebird (*Fregata magnificens*)
260 nestlings [58]. Authors however, found no variation in nitric oxide in infected birds, and so
261 herpesvirus infection may not activated pathways that would triggered an increase in ROS, leading
262 then to telomere shortening. The researchers hypothesized lower metabolic rate due to slow
263 growth of frigatebird might have masked the effects of infection on telomere. In this view, the
264 supposed high metabolism of our blue tit nestlings [59] may have accelerated the effect of
265 infection on telomere. In addition, observations on siskins (*Spinus spinus*) [60] and great reed
266 warblers (*Acrocephalus arundinaceus*) [36] suffering from malaria, showed a reduction in telomere
267 length in erythrocytes compared to uninfected conspecifics, and malaria seem to be associated to
268 ROS increasing [61]. In fact, inflammation exacerbate the rate of telomere attrition, leading to
269 telomere dysfunction and accelerating cellular aging process[62].

270 Generally, oxidative stress might contribute to telomere shortening, as supported by a meta-
271 analysis by Armstrong and Boonekamp [63]. However, as commented by Reichert and Stier in their
272 review [64], our understanding of this link remains incomplete. Indeed, in our study, although
273 telomere length dynamics were measured over 7 days, the simulated infection had an effect only
274 over two days. Given this very short time for oxidative stress to act on telomeres, we question to
275 what extent shortening has been a consequences of ROS or to an increase in blood leukocytes,
276 which their rapidly division as immune response might led to shorten their telomeres. However, in
277 avian blood, a normal hematocrit ranges from 40 to 60%, and the general ratio of red blood cells
278 to white blood cells is around 100 erythrocytes to 1 leucocyte [65]. Since avian erythrocytes are
279 nucleated, the majority of DNA extracted from blood originates from them, therefore, even minor
280 changes in leukocytes proportion because infections should have little impact on average telomere
281 length of blood DNA. However, this hypothesis should not be underestimated, since we do not know
282 the extension of the increase of white blood cells after Poly I:C challenge. Anyhow, a correlative
283 analysis in our dataset shows a lack of covariation between number of leukocytes and telomere
284 length variation between day 8 and 15 ($r = -0.02$, $r^2 = 0.00$, $p = 0.913$), which suggests no
285 impact of changes in blood cell population on telomere dynamics. Although the mechanism leading
286 immune response to telomere shortening in is still unclear, this study might support the “ageing
287 cost of infections pathway” hypothesis suggested by Giraudeau and colleagues [22], which states
288 infections may lead to faster biological ageing. Our finding suggest that immune responses may

289 accelerate telomere shortening, and that causative factors could be the production of ROS
290 downstream by the binding of the receptor TRL3 and the high metabolism of blue tit nestlings.
291 Since nestlings telomere shortening has been shown to reflect individual survival probability to
292 adulthood [66], this biomarker could underline current individual health state and trade-offs
293 between immune responses to infection and premature biological senescence. To validate this post-
294 hoc observation we described, we encourage further studies on how telomere length dynamics are
295 altered by experimental activation of immune system.

296

297 **Ethics**

298 Blood sampling and handling did not lead to any high discomfort in animals which we were able to
299 observed to the best of our skills. We noticed no desertion of parents resulting from the brood
300 manipulation. This research complies with the current laws on animal experimentation in the
301 Netherlands and European Union and the experiments was carried out in accordance with EU
302 Directive 2010/63/EU for animal experiments. The manuscript is reported in accordance with
303 ARRIVE guidelines. The permissions for the handling and experimental manipulation of the birds
304 were provided by University of Wageningen and the work was approved by the Animal Ethic
305 committee of Wageningen University (approval ref. 2022.W-0037.00). The work was carried out by
306 qualified and adequately trained personnel in accordance with current legislation.

307

308 **Data accessibility**

309 Data, metadata and code are provided in the electronic supplementary material.

310

311 **Authors' contributions**

312 M.S., S.R. and N.V.D.B. designed the study. M.S. conducted the field work, lab work and wrote the
313 first version of the paper. S.R. conducted field work and lab work. I.M.E supported laboratory
314 analysis and fieldwork. N.V.D.B. led the project. All the authors were involved in the revision and
315 approval of the final draft of the paper and agreed to be held accountable for the work performed
316 therein

317

318 **Competing interests**

319 We declare no competing interests.

320

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332

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